

1 **IL-1b intervention for TNF resistance in IBD.**

2 Pre-Clinical/Clinical/Translational/Phase1-3
3 Compassionate Use Document (FDA format)

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8 1. The concept presented and being tested in this proposal is that excess production of the
9 inflammatory cytokine interleukin-1beta is a source of treatment failure (“resistance”) in inflammatory
10 bowel disease following treatment with a TNF-alpha inhibitor (e.g., infliximab).

11 2. Compassionate Use, also known as Expanded Access, provides access to an investigational
12 therapeutic (drug) when a life threatening condition exists and no comparable medication is available for
13 treatment.

14 3. The major requirements for Compassionate Use are:

- 15 a. The patient or patients has/have a life-threatening disease or medical condition.
- 16 b. There is no comparable or satisfactory alternative therapy
- 17 c. The potential benefit outweighs the potential risks
- 18 d. The use does not interfere with initiation, conduct or completion of clinical investigations.

19 4. It is estimated that on average 99% of Expanded Access (Compassionate Use) are approved by
20 the FDA (Food and Drug Administration).

21 5. We used cells from healthy individuals and authentic tissues from affected patient cohorts,
22 measuring total transcription in response to blockade of TNF-alpha or in response to exposure to a
23 cytokine, like TNF-alpha or interferon gamma (IFNg) to study feedback and resistance mechanisms to
24 therapeutic (clinical) TNF-alpha inhibition in humans.

- 25 a. Model systems were used only to conceptualize systems biologic concepts and provide information
26 regarding minimal components within an immunologic network.

27 6. The transcriptome-wide analysis also included discovery of individual gene targets likely to
28 function in conferring resistance to first-line biologic agents in gastroenterology.

29 7. For this approach, we measured total transcription using microarray in patient cells and tissues
30 resistant to infliximab or another biologic targeting TNF-alpha.

- 31 a. In this proposal, we focus on resistance to TNFa inhibition by agents like infliximab, etanercept,
32 adalimumab or golimumab.
- 33 b. Resistance to biological targeting IL-23 like guselkumab is less well understood and addressed
34 separately.

35 8. We integrated findings from measurements of total transcription in separate cellular systems to
36 produce a concise and accurate biological description of cytokine interconnectedness and feedback
37 mechanisms in immunologic signaling.

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